

A Review on Vision-Based Methods for Road Pothole Detection and Lane Detection Using YOLOv8 Deep Learning Algorithm

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Abstract— The techniques used for road anomaly identification have changed significantly as a result of the growing advances in computer vision and deep learning, especially in the areas of pothole and lane recognition. This review article offers a thorough analysis of vision-based methods applied to improve road safety, with particular attention on the incorporation of the YOLOv8 deep learning algorithm. The literature study highlights the critical importance of vision-based systems in contemporary transportation infrastructure while examining various approaches and difficulties related to road anomaly detection. Existing methods that make use of specialized sensors, smartphone sensors, and machine learning integration are evaluated critically, with an emphasis on their advantages and disadvantages. Using the Roboflow public library to generate annotated pothole photos, the methodology section describes the pre-processing processes for the dataset. The object identification model used is YOLOv8, which requires a change in annotation format from Pascal VOC to COCO. To have a better grasp of YOLOx's working principles, its architecture which includes its head, spine, and one-stage object detection is explained.

Keywords : Computer Vision-based methods, Pothole detection, Lane detection, YOLOv8, Deep learning algorithms, Transportation, Machine learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

The state of roads has a substantial influence on both safety and the integrity of vehicles, making them essential parts of transportation networks. Because of a confluence of weather and traffic, potholes are a common threat to road infrastructure, increasing the risk of car damage and endangering driver safety. The Korea Express Corporation research, which found that between 2015 and 2019, there were almost 47,200 potholes on Korean expressways, serves as an example of the problem's seriousness. This concerning number equates to almost 10 potholes per kilometre on South Korea's 4767-kilometer highway network. Moreover, official records from 2017 to 2019 showed 221 traffic incidents caused by potholes, highlighting the real dangers connected to road imperfections.

Potholes are a problem that requires proactive detection and control. Four essential processes are involved in a thorough pothole detection process: data collection, data preprocessing, feature extraction, and pothole categorization. Creating a dataset

from different sensor data or photos that are essential for understanding and evaluating potholes is the data acquisition step. Filtering and masking are two signal-processing methods that are used in the next phase of data preparation to modify raw data. The next step is feature extraction, which looks for characteristics in the pre-processed data that set potholes apart from non-potholes. Pothole classification, the last phase, uses accuracy-optimized algorithms to identify the presence of potholes.

Fig. General Process of Pothole Detection

Throughout this process, data sensing and processing are essential components that impact the kind and effectiveness of pothole detection. As such, methods based on efficient data sensing and processing are considered vital. Figure 1 summarizes the complex process of pothole detection by showing the several procedures that must be taken.

From manual visual inspections by human specialists to automated processes utilizing cutting-edge technologies, pothole identification has changed throughout time. Interestingly, three widely used automated techniques for detecting potholes have been developed: vibration-based, vision-based, and 3D reconstruction-based techniques. This essay compares and contrasts these three approaches in order to shed light on each one's advantages and disadvantages. Section 2 provides a comparative study, and Section 3 explores the technology and detection methods related to each approach, summarizing the latest developments. Section 3 summarizes the features and efficacy of current automated pothole detecting studies. Section 4 provides insights into future directions for study and growth in this important area as the report comes to a close.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Road anomaly detection and monitoring, in particular the monitoring of potholes, have become essential components of infrastructure upkeep and road safety. This study of the literature attempts to give a thorough overview of current methods, together with an analysis of their advantages, disadvantages, and future problems. Since road safety is a big issue, road pothole and lane detection utilizing vision-based approaches has grown more relevant. Given the limitations of existing approaches, real-time detection can be enhanced by the application of deep learning techniques, particularly YOLOv8.

1. Methods for Road Pothole Detection

Comparing Automated Techniques for Detecting Potholes

With the introduction of automatic techniques that all make use of different technology, pothole detection has advanced significantly. Three popular automatic pothole-detection techniques are compared in this section: vibration-based, vision-based, and 3D reconstruction-based.

1.1 Vision-Based Method:

The principle underlying the application of image processing and deep learning techniques to photos or videos involves utilizing advanced algorithms to analyze visual data. This approach proves to be advantageous due to its cost-effectiveness in comparison to 3D rebuilding methods, making it particularly suitable for discerning the quantity and types of potholes in a given area. However, the technique has inherent weaknesses stemming from its reliance on two-dimensional information, which poses limitations in accurately determining depth and volume. Additionally, the analysis is susceptible to the influence of shadows and illumination patterns, potentially affecting the precision of the results. It is crucial to bear in mind that, while vision-based techniques offer efficiency and cost savings, they are constrained in their ability to capture specific features of potholes, emphasizing the need for complementary methods in comprehensive pothole detection and assessment.

1.3 3D Reconstruction-Based Method:

The application of stereo-vision technology forms the foundation of an approach that aims to estimate the volume and predict the shape of potholes. This method boasts strengths, particularly in achieving the highest degree of accuracy when it comes to measuring volume and predicting the form of potholes. However, it comes with certain drawbacks, notably being more expensive than alternative approaches. Additionally, the technique encounters challenges in identifying potholes that may be covered in soil or water, as indicated in the literature. Despite its superior accuracy, the 3D reconstruction-based approach is hindered by issues of affordability and environmental suitability, emphasizing the need for a balanced consideration of cost and adaptability in choosing a pothole detection methodology.

1.2 Vibration-Based Method:

The principle underlying the use of a vehicle's acceleration sensor for pothole detection involves leveraging data from the sensor to ascertain the presence of potholes and estimate their depth. This approach offers notable strengths, as it is the least expensive among the three methods considered. Additionally, the real-time processing of data and lower storage requirements make it a practical choice for efficient implementation. However, certain weaknesses are associated with this technique, including challenges in precisely defining the shapes of potholes, and variations arising from differences in vehicles and sensors used during the data-acquisition process. It is important to note that the vibration-based technique, while cost-effective, may not excel in detailed form detection, underscoring the need for a comprehensive understanding of its limitations in addressing specific nuances of pothole characteristics.

Figure : Characteristics of Automated Pothole-Detection

Table: Characteristics of Automated Pothole-Detection

Methods

Methods	Strengths	Weaknesses
Vision-based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cost-effective compared to 3D reconstruction - Suitable for determining number and approximate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limitations in measuring volume and depth due to two-dimensional data - Affected by lighting and shadow conditions shape of potholes
Vibration-based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Most cost-effective among the three methods - Real-time data processing can be applied - Requires small storage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limitations in providing the exact shape of potholes - Affected by sensor and vehicle variations

Based on particular needs and limitations, this comparison analysis and related factors offer insightful guidance for choosing a suitable pothole-detection technique.

2. The Three Types of Recent Automated Pothole-Detection Methods

This section explores the latest automated techniques for detecting potholes, with a particular emphasis on the vision-based method. Numerous research works have put forward innovative methods, all of which have advanced the field of pothole identification.

2.1. Vision-Based Method (Type A)

Lim et al. [1] Using photos as input data, Lim et al. developed automatic deep learning-based pothole detecting techniques. Their dataset was gathered from open databases and included 996 training and 203 testing photos. The original YOLOv2 was outperformed in terms of average accuracy, recall, and frames per second (FPS) by two modified YOLOv2 models: an anchor-box model and a denser-grid model. The study's disadvantage is that it was trained on a small dataset, although demonstrating higher performance. This calls for more research on real-time pothole identification using a larger dataset.

Baek et al. [2] A method for detecting and classifying potholes using edge detection on pavement photos was presented by Baek et al. Road damage feature extraction, road damage categorization, and picture preprocessing were the three stages of the procedure. Their method demonstrated an average classification accuracy of 0.7786 and a mean-squared error (MSE) of 0.2–0.44 when tested on the Global Road Damage Detection Challenge 2020 dataset. The study found that although it could recognize pothole forms, it was not able to reliably estimate pothole sizes. This has led to further work on detailed feature extraction for size prediction.

Park et al. [3] A pothole identification technique using three distinct YOLO models—YOLOv4, YOLOv4-tiny, and YOLOv5—was presented by Park et al. The evaluation showed that YOLOv4-tiny performed better, based on mean average accuracy at 50% intersection-over-union threshold (mAP@0.5). The research recognized the lack of trials conducted in inclement weather and the difficulty in spotting tiny potholes at a distance. These results highlight the need for enhanced durability and identification of minor potholes in harsh environmental settings.

Wanli Ye et al. [4] Using a dataset of 96,000 pictures, Wanli Ye et al. presented an automated pothole identification technique with prepooling CNN. Their approach, which highlighted the benefits of prepooling CNN versus traditional CNN, showed increased accuracy. Additionally, the prepooling CNN demonstrated robustness to changing pavement and light circumstances. According to the study, CNN-based approaches are more suited for pothole identification than more conventional methods like

K-means clustering and Sobel edge detection. Future research will investigate real-time implementation on inexpensive edge devices.

Hanshen Chen et al. [5] A pothole identification technique based on location-aware convolutional neural networks was presented by Hanshen Chen et al. Using a public pothole dataset, the method achieved good accuracy (0.950) and precision (0.952) by using two subnetworks, namely PCNN and LCNN. The approach demonstrated scalability in identifying different types of road discomfort. Performance deterioration with low-resolution input data was one of the challenges, indicating the need for further study incorporating cascade approaches and scale choices for better detection performance.

Deepak Kumar Dewangan et al. [6] A CNN-based pothole identification technique utilizing an embedded car prototype equipped with a monocular camera and Raspberry Pi was proposed by Deepak Kumar Dewangan et al. The approach showed great precision (0.9903), recall (0.9903), accuracy (0.9902), and F1 score (0.9833) using a dataset of 3915 pictures. The work demonstrated promise for real-time pothole detection on inexpensive edge devices like Jetson Nano by optimizing the CNN architecture for hardware needs.

Nhat-Duc Hoang [7] suggested machine learning-based pothole detection techniques that make use of LS-SVM and ANN. With an AUC of 0.96 for LS-SVM and 0.92 for ANN, the study produced classification accuracy rates (CAR) of 88.75% for LS-SVM and 85.25% for ANN. Subsequent research will examine sophisticated artificial intelligence models to improve accuracy and utilize visual signal processing methods to estimate size.

2.2. Additional Studies on Pothole Detection

Wanly Ye and colleagues - Prepooling CNN for Pothole Detection [8] A prepooled Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based pothole detection system was proposed by Wanly Ye et al. The study demonstrated the resilience of their method using a sizable dataset consisting of 24,000 photos for testing and 96,000 images for training. Their technique produced an optimum precision of 0.9895 and an average precision of more than 0.80. The system configuration included of an 8GB GeForce

GTX 1080 GPU, 32GB RAM, and an Intel Core i7-8750H CPU. The prepooled CNN's benefits were emphasized, especially its ability to withstand variations in pavement conditions and illumination, which presents a viable method for pothole identification.

Lim et al. - Location-Aware CNN for Pothole Detection [9] A pothole identification technique based on location-aware Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) was presented by Hanshen Chen et al. Two subnetworks were included in their method: a part-based classification network (PCNN) and a localization network (LCNN). Their technique showed great accuracy (0.950), precision (0.952), recall (0.920), and F1 score (0.936) using a dataset of 5,676 pictures. Notably, the suggested approach showed scalability by identifying additional road irregularities in addition to potholes. The scientists noted that there were challenges, such as low-resolution input data, and they suggested further study including sophisticated algorithms to enhance detection performance.

Maeda et al. - CNN-Based Pothole Detection with Embedded Vehicle Prototype [10] A CNN-based pothole identification technique using an embedded car prototype equipped with a Raspberry Pi and a monocular camera unit was presented by Deepak Kumar Dewangan et al. Their 3,915-image dataset was subjected to conventional data augmentation methods. With an accuracy of 0.9902, precision of 0.9903, recall of 0.9903, and an F1 score of 0.9833, the suggested approach produced impressive results. The versatility of their low-cost edge device-based real-time pothole detecting method was highlighted by the authors. The foundation for successful and affordable in-car pothole detecting systems was established by this study.

Rahman - Pothole Detection with Machine Learning Algorithms [11] suggested machine learning-based pothole identification techniques, namely Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and Least-Squares Support-Vector Machines (LS-SVM). With 200 photos used for training and testing, the study's classification accuracy rates were 85.25% (ANN) and 88.75% (LS-SVM). AUC, or area under the curve, is one evaluation statistic that was taken into consideration. The limits of the study were acknowledged, and recommendations for future research were made to improve accuracy through the use of sophisticated AI models and

sophisticated image-signal-processing techniques to estimate pothole sizes.

Penghui Wang et al. - Pothole Detection with Wavelet Energy Field [12] Based on a wavelet energy field, Penghui Wang et al. presented a technique for segmenting and detecting potholes in asphalt pavement. Their approach, which used 120 pavement photos, showed how to use geometric criteria and morphological processing to effectively locate and separate potholes. The suggested approach produced results with a recall of 0.875, precision of 0.833, and total accuracy of 0.867. The study pointed several areas in need of development and recommended investigating more potent mathematical models to raise pothole detecting accuracy.

Muhammad Haroon Yousaf et al. - Pothole Detection and Localization [13] Using pavement photos, Muhammad Haroon Yousaf et al. suggested a technique for pothole identification and location. Pothole localization and pavement-image categorization were the two main procedures in their method. High recall (0.941), precision (0.970), and accuracy (0.957) were attained by the study. By utilizing cutting-edge strategies like support vector machines (SVM) and the bag-of-words approach, the suggested solution outperformed the current ones. It was recommended that future research employ cutting-edge texture-based methods to enhance pothole identification even further.

III. CONCLUSION

3.1 Conclusions and Future Directions

Together, the given research offer a variety of approaches and technology that advance the field of automated pothole identification. Every approach demonstrated its advantages and disadvantages, opening the door for further developments in this field.

Insights from Vision-Based Methods

Research using vision-based techniques, as those by Baek et al. [2], Park et al. [3], and Lim et al. [1], showed how well deep learning—specifically, YOLO variants—performed in identifying potholes. These algorithms made use of large datasets and improved accuracy by applying methods including edge

detection, classification, and picture preprocessing. Significantly, Park et al.'s study's performance of YOLOv4-tiny suggested the possibility of real-time applications. Nonetheless, issues such as the small dataset size and susceptibility to unfavourable weather were noted, indicating potential directions for further investigation.

Strengths and Limitations of Vibration-Based Methods

Vibration-based techniques, such those demonstrated by Baek et al.'s research [2], provide affordable solutions with real-time data processing. For pothole identification, these techniques depend on information from vehicle acceleration sensors. Although they are beneficial in terms of resource efficiency, they have difficulties in precisely identifying the geometry of potholes. Results might be affected by differences in the sensor and the vehicle, which emphasizes the necessity for more improvement and robustness testing.

Precision in 3D Reconstruction-Based Methods

The technique of Baek et al. [2] that relied on 3D reconstruction performed exceptionally well in forecasting pothole forms and precisely calculating their volumes. But its high cost and difficulties in unfavorable situations, including wet potholes, suggest that improvement and flexibility are necessary before it can be widely used.

3.2 Future Directions

Combining Different Technologies

The constraints of vibration-based, vision-based, and 3D reconstruction techniques may be addressed by their confluence. Integrating the advantages of these methods might result in a pothole-detection system that is stronger and more thorough.

Implementation in Real-Time

With road conditions changing constantly, efforts should be focused on implementing pothole detection in real-time. Deepak Kumar Dewangan et al.'s [21] demonstration of the use of edge devices offers a promising avenue for the implementation of reasonably priced in-vehicle detection systems.

Unfavorable Situations and Expanding the Dataset

Subsequent investigations need to concentrate on augmenting the resilience of approaches for detecting potholes in unfavorable weather and illumination circumstances. Furthermore, broadening datasets to encompass a variety of circumstances, road kinds, and environmental obstacles would enhance the detection algorithms' generalization and dependability.

Cooperation Across Disciplines

The development of workable, market-ready solutions can be aided by partnerships between transportation authorities, civil engineers, and computer vision specialists. Pothole-detection systems that combine technical know-how with domain-specific insights can be more useful and effective.

3.3 Final Thoughts

The evaluated research conclude that there has been a substantial advancement in automated pothole identification, highlighting the potential for better road upkeep and safety. While every approach has its own advantages and disadvantages, breakthroughs in the sector will come from a concerted effort toward integration, real-time deployment, and tackling unfavorable situations. To fully utilize automated pothole-detection technology, multidisciplinary cooperation between researchers, engineers, and policymakers is essential.

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